

Social and Private Benefits of Sea Ice Information in Arctic Shipping: An Avoided Costs Analysis

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Abstract:

Driven by melting sea ice, Arctic shipping has grown by approximately 6% annually over the past decade. This has increased the demand for sea ice information which is crucial for ships navigating in icy waters. Besides improving safety, such information can enable more cost-efficient voyages and reduce negative externalities of shipping including CO₂ emissions. However, there is narrow literature considering these socioeconomic benefits of sea ice information. Thus, the aim of this thesis is to assess the potential social and private benefits of sea ice information in the Arctic region using the avoided costs assessment framework. Social benefits are evaluated through saved CO₂ emission costs and private benefits through fuel cost savings using a monthly-aggregated AIS-based dataset from 2023 of individual vessels, along with historical price data.

The results show how much reduced shipping distance and power usage can decrease fuel and CO₂ emission costs in the Arctic. Every additional 1% avoided in total fuel consumption saves annually €2.8 million in fuel costs and €940 000 in CO₂ costs when considering the entire Arctic region. The EEZ-level analysis reveals that the greatest benefits, in terms of avoided costs, occur in the Alaskan EEZ, while the ship type-level analysis indicates that bulk carriers generate highest avoided costs. The benefits of sea ice information in the future are dependent on multiple factors that contain substantial uncertainty related to matters such as climate change, governance issues and policy regulations of the Arctic. The scenario analysis conducted for the period from 2024 to 2100 shows that the present value of the benefits of sea ice information significantly outweighs the present value of costs of a representative sea ice service across the considered scenarios. Overall, the results indicate that producing sea ice information is feasible. However, there are uncertainties that require further research.

This thesis contributes to the climate service valuation literature by promoting the understanding of the benefits and feasibility of sea ice information services in the Arctic region. This thesis further contributes to the discussion on sustainable maritime practices by providing insights into the cost efficiency of utilizing sea ice information to reduce CO₂ emissions.

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Tiivistelmä:

Merijään sulamisen myötä, arktinen laivaliikenne on kasvanut keskimäärin 6% vuosittain viimeisen vuosikymmenen aikana. Tämä on kasvattanut kysyntää merijäätidolle, joka on tärkeää jäisillä vesialueilla kulkeville aluksille. Turvallisuuden parantamisen lisäksi, merijäätiö voi mahdollistaa kustannustehokkaampia matkoja ja vähentää laivaliikenteen negatiivisia ulkoisvaikutuksia kuten CO₂-päästöjä. Merijäätidon sosioekonomisia hyötyjä käsittelevä aiempi tutkimuskirjallisuus on kuitenkin suppea. Tämän tutkielman tavoitteena on arvioida merijäätidon potentiaalisia yhteiskunnallisia ja yksityisiä hyötyjä käyttäen vältettyjen kustannusten menetelmää. Yhteiskunnallisia hyötyjä arvioidaan vältettyinä CO₂-kustannuksina ja yksityisiä hyötyjä vältettyinä polttoainekustannuksina hyödyntämällä kuukausitasolla aggregoitua AIS-dataan perustuvaa aineistoa yksittäisistä aluksista vuodelta 2023 sekä historiallista hinta-aineistoa.

Tulokset osoittavat kuinka paljon matkan lyheneminen ja pienempi konetehto voi vähentää polttoaine- ja CO₂-kustannuksia arktisella alueella. Jokainen kokonaispolttoainekulutuksessa vähennetty prosenttiyksikkö tuottaa vuosittain vältettyjä polttoainekustannuksia €2.8 miljoonaa ja vastaavasti vältettyjä CO₂-kustannuksia €940 000, kun tarkastellaan koko arktista aluetta. Yksinomaisia talousvyöhykkeitä (engl. Exclusive Economic Zone, EEZ) tarkasteleva analyysi osoittaa, että suurimmat hyödyt vältettyinä kustannuksina saavutetaan Alaskan talousvyöhykkeellä, ja laivatyyppejä tarkasteleva analyysi indikoi irtolastialuksille suurimpia vältettyjä kustannuksia. Merijäätidon hyödyt tulevaisuudessa riippuvat useasta tekijästä, joihin liittyy epävarmuutta koskien muuan muassa ilmastonmuutosta, hallinnollisia haasteita ja poliittisia säädöksiä arktisella alueella. Vuosille 2024–2100 suoritettu skenaarioanalyysi osoittaa, että merijäätidon hyötyjen nykyarvo ylittää merijääpalvelun kustannukset tarkastelluissa skenaarioissa. Kaiken kaikkiaan, tulokset osoittavat, että merijäätidon tuottaminen on kannattavaa. Tuloksiin liittyy kuitenkin paljon epävarmuutta vaatien jatkotutkimusta.

Tämä tutkielma edistää ilmastopalveluiden arvottamistutkimusta lisäämällä ymmärrystä merijääpalveluiden hyödyistä ja kannattavuudesta arktisella alueella. Lisäksi tutkielma edistää keskustelua kestävästä merenkulun käytännöistä tarjoamalla näkemyksiä merijäätidon kustannustehokkuudesta CO₂-päästöjen vähentämiseksi.

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1 Introduction

As the Arctic Sea ice has been losing its extent and thickness, access to the Arctic has expanded, increasing economic opportunities and maritime activity in the area (Lavengood, 2021). The Arctic waters can provide shorter transit times as well as lower fuel and overall costs compared to alternative southern routes (Chen et al., 2023). In fact, containerships using the Northern Sea Route (NSR) can save 40% in distance compared to southern routes such as the Suez Canal Route (SCR) (Furuichi & Otsuka, 2015; Schøyen & Bråthen, 2011). Globally, ships carry 90% of world trade in goods and 80% by value between non-neighbouring countries (OECD, 2013). It is predicted that 4.7% of shipping trade will be in the Arctic region by 2030 (Bekkers et al., 2018). Additionally, Arctic marine activity increases as vessels have improved access to natural resources including hydrocarbons, minerals and living resources such as fish populations. Resource extraction and shipping are the two key economic outputs of the Arctic. In addition, Arctic tourism and military training activity has increased (Lavengood, 2021; Berkman and Young, 2009). The current and future economic activity in the Arctic is affected among other things by climate change, natural resource development, governance challenges as well as by economic factors, geopolitical tensions and regulatory frameworks (AMSA report, 2009; Stephenson & Smith, 2015; Jiang et al., 2020; Dyck, 2024).

Growing shipping activity in the Arctic increases environmental challenges associated with shipping including its impacts on climate change, air quality, and marine biodiversity. Ice conditions force vessels to slow down and consume more fuel. Moreover, inaccessible ice-covered areas can force ships to make detours in search of navigable routes, leading to further increases in fuel consumption (Theocharis et al., 2018; Furuichi & Otsuka, 2015; AMSA Report, 2009). In 2018, global shipping emitted 1 076 million tonnes of CO₂ which equals to around 2.9% of global emissions caused by human activities (European Commission, 2024a). In 2023 the International Maritime Organization (IMO) published a revised greenhouse gas (GHG) strategy which states that the CO₂ emissions caused by international shipping globally, is targeted to reach a reduction of 20% striving for 30% by 2030 and 70% striving for 80% by 2040, compared to the level of 2008. In addition, a target to reach net-zero emissions from international shipping by or around 2050 has been set (IMO, 2023). On the other hand, CO₂ emissions of shipping are predicted to grow 50–250% and up

to 15% of total CO₂ emissions is expected to be attributable to maritime transport by 2050 (IMO, 2014). This contradiction highlights a significant challenge as the shipping industry continues to expand and simultaneously faces the imperative to reduce emissions as part of climate change mitigation efforts (Wu et al. 2020).

Weather and climate information can play a crucial role in increasing efficiency in polar activities along with managing risks caused by ice (Haavisto et al., 2020). Products and services that inform where the ice is going to be, how closely packed it is and how thick and strong it is, are key information elements for the operator in decision-making when estimating how difficult it will be to go around or through the ice (AMSA Report, 2009). In shipping, shorter geographical distances result in reduced transit times, lower operating costs, and potentially decreased fuel consumption, which in turn reduces CO₂ and other GHG emissions (Theocharis et al., 2018).

The goal of this thesis is to evaluate the benefits of sea ice information in Arctic shipping. Specifically, it aims to estimate the private and social benefits of each additional 1% reduction in total fuel consumption over a specified timeframe. Using the avoided costs framework, the thesis seeks to answer the key research question:

How much can be saved in private costs through fuel savings and in social costs through CO₂ reductions by using sea ice information in the Arctic?

The results of this thesis can be utilized in the Arctic PASSION project which develops an observation system in the Arctic. Additionally, the results can help ship operators recognize the role of sea ice information in managing cost flows, while also enabling regulators to understand better the economic importance of sea ice information services in climate change mitigation and adaptation efforts.

This thesis is structured as follows: In chapter 2, the background is presented. Chapter 3 introduces the framework of climate service evaluation as well as previous relevant economic literature. Chapter 4 covers the data, while Chapter 5 details the methods used in the analysis. Chapter 6 presents the results, followed by the discussion in Chapter 7. Finally, Chapter 8 concludes the thesis.

2 Background

This chapter provides an overview of the key framework, starting with an introduction about arctic navigation conditions. This is followed by an overview of climate and sea ice information and services. Finally, the chapter presents the private and external costs related to Arctic shipping.

2.1 Navigation conditions

Weather and environmental conditions are extremely hazardous for Arctic shipping, with ice perhaps presenting the highest risk of all (Ghosh & Rubly, 2015). In fact, Arctic shipping is widely dependent on ice conditions and ice will continue to act as the single greatest obstacle to navigation in the Arctic (Zhao et al., 2022; Meng et al., 2016). The highest risk times of the year for vessels are during break-up (April and May), while summer and autumn are the safest and most economical seasons for marine activity in the Arctic (AMSA Report, 2009; Arctic PASSION, 2024b). However, Müller et al. (2023) show that there is a shift from seasonal to year-round shipping, emphasizing the growing number of winter sailings.

The shipping season's lengthening has widened access to the Northern Sea Route (NSR) in the Eurasian Arctic and the North-West Passage (NWP) in the American and Canadian archipelago (Lavengood, 2021). The Transpolar Sea Route (TSR) could become viable by the middle of the 21st century, or potentially as early as 2040, due to the continued retreat of sea ice in the Arctic Ocean (Bennett et al., 2020; Stephenson et al., 2013; Li & Lynch, 2023). The most shipping days per month in the Arctic waters occur along the NSR, Chukchi-Bering Sea, West Greenland and Svalbard (Müller et al., 2023) or as according to another source along the North-East Passage (NEP), particularly in the Kara and Barents Seas (Huntington et al., 2023). It is important to note that literature defines the Arctic region using varying boundaries, with particular inconsistency regarding whether the Baltic Sea or parts of it are included. Compared to European and Russian Arctic areas, the Canadian area and the NWP have significantly less traffic. This is mainly because of the higher variability in ice conditions, limited maritime and navigational infrastructure as well as because of its remoteness compared to other areas (Mussells et al., 2017).

During the past decade Arctic shipping has increased by 7% per year in shipping days and 6% in individual ships in the Polar Code Area (Müller et al., 2023). In 2014, 9.3% of the world's shipping traffic located in the Arctic waters (Eguíluz et al., 2016). Figure 1 presents the shipping activity in 2023 when the sea ice was at its broadest and at its narrowest.

Figure 1. Shipping activity in the Arctic in 1a) September and 1b) March (2023). The different colours illustrate different ship types. The definitions of the colours: Chemical tankers=red, Gas tankers=blue, Bulk carriers=orange, General cargo ships=dark blue, Container ships=green, Ro-Ro cargo ships=pink, Refrigerated cargo ships=turquoise, Offshore supply ships=purple, Other service offshore vessels=grey, Other activities=light brown, fishing vessels=dark green, crude oil tankers=dark brown, oil product tankers=dark red, passenger ships=light yellow, cruise ships=yellow. Source: PAME, ASTD.

Despite the opportunities caused by melting ice, the Arctic is ice covered for the largest part of the year, causing uncertainties that reduce the attractiveness of Arctic routes. Especially for round services or trips with a fixed schedule and transit time, reliability, predictability and staying on schedule cannot be guaranteed on routes with ice (Meng et al., 2016). Ice and its thickness also reduce the speed of the vessel which means that compared to southern routes the savings on fuel consumption and transit time might be lower than expected (Cariou et al., 2021; Furuichi & Otsuka, 2015). Large bulk carriers have a design speed of around 14 knots (26 km/h), while container ships one of approximately 27 knots (50 km/h) (Lindstad et al., 2012). The design speed of a vessel is the maximum speed in ice-free areas. It is also recommended to navigate at a slower speed on the transarctic routes. The so-called slow steaming can save costs and reduce emissions. However, at low speed, the total transit time may increase and thus cause higher capital cost. Furthermore, navigation is challenged by significant year-to-year variability in sea ice extent, and by the unevenly distributed ice in different

regions. In summer, floating ice threatens ships whereas prevalent ice in the winter (Meng et al., 2016).

Besides ice, characteristic factors of Arctic shipping are low air and water temperatures, highly variable and often unpredictable severe weather, magnetic variation, solar flare activity, and extended periods of daylight or darkness. The mean temperature varies in January from -5°C along the north coast of Norway to greater than -35°C in central Greenland, the northern part of the Canadian Archipelago, and in northern Siberia (AMSA Report, 2009). Also, remoteness and long distances to ports are major risk factors in Arctic shipping, with the most hazardous areas being the farthest from existing ports (Christensen et al., 2022).

Vessels sailing in the Arctic need to fulfil certain technical requirements such as reinforced hulls, powerful engines and overall performance through ice. These requirements are related to the vessel's ice class. The ice class is a certification provided by a Maritime administration or a classification society. The class is based on specific set of ice-class rules such as Finnish-Swedish Ice Class Rules, the Russian Maritime Register of Ships and the Polar Class Rules developed by the International Association of Classification Societies (IACS) (Solakivi et al., 2018; AMSA Report, 2009). The Polar Class (PC) ships are distributed into seven categories by their intended ship operation and the level of ice in the area they operate. The highest polar class is PC1. The Polar Class 6 as defined in IACS system is equivalent to 1A Super as defined by the Finnish-Swedish Ice Class rules whereby PC7 corresponds to 1A (Trafi, 2017). The accessibility among vessels that have medium or little strengthening when sailing along the NWP has increased substantially particularly in early season just after ice break-up and just before freeze-up (Dawson et al. 2022). It is predicted that PC6 ships will be able to sail the Arctic shipping routes year-round by 2070 under the climate scenario in which the decadal-averaged global mean surface temperature anomaly hits approximately $+3.6^{\circ}\text{C}$ (under SSP585) compared to pre-industrial times (Min et al., 2022).

According to an unpublished report (Arctic PASSION, 2024b), a recent trend shows increased shipping activity in high-risk ice conditions which are primarily found in the Russian Arctic and eastern Greenland. Non-ice-strengthened fishing vessels are the most frequently observed ship type operating in these risky conditions, followed by medium ice-strengthened cargo vessels and tankers. The report highlights that

information about the riskiness of the ice conditions is especially valuable for vessels with lower polar classifications.

2.2 Sea ice information

The microeconomics of information has originally outgrown from the economic theory of uncertainty (Hirshleifer, 1973). Uncertainty is the dispersion of individual's subjective probability distributions over possible states of the world and information tends to change these distributions (Repo, 1989). In this sense information can be defined as a negative measure of uncertainty.

Climate information refers to data and knowledge about past, present and future climatic conditions and trends. These include weather forecasts, climate projections, historical climate data and information on climate variability and extreme events (Hansen et al., 2019; WMO, 2014). Climate and meteorological information services (or systems), on the other hand, integrate climate and weather data to provide timely and relevant information for decision-making (WMO, 2014). They consist of information including meteorological variables such as temperature, rainfall, wind, cloudiness and other atmospheric variables. Marine weather and climate services cover hazards like high waves, currents, storm surge/coastal inundation and sea ice. All weather and climate forecasts can be presented in words, numbers or graphical form and the expression can be in categorical or probabilistic terms (Anderson et al., 2015). While information refers to the content provided through products and services (Repo, 1987), information products like weather forecast apps, are economic goods that can be produced, stored, consumed, invested in, or sold (Birchler & Bütler, 2007).

The use of meteorological, hydrological, oceanographic and related information can provide substantial benefits to society as it enables to take decisions which reduce the impacts of natural hazards (Anderson et al., 2015). In the Arctic context, it is generally noted that there is a need for data from an Arctic observing network to support stakeholders with planning and action (Eicken et al., 2009; Starkweather et al., 2022). As the Arctic traffic increases, the need for valuable weather, water, ice and climate information (WWIC) services in the Arctic increases along. For maritime users in the Arctic waters, information about ice conditions is the main interest. However, compared to other WWIC services, ice information is much less frequently available, more uncertain, and less accurate (Knol et al., 2018; Lamers et al., 2018).

The accessibility, understandability, usefulness, and reliability of environmental information systems are key factors that determine the vessel operator's ability to avoid hazardous weather and ice-conditions (Müller et al., 2023). Although the ice parameters needed in the Arctic are expected to stay the same in the future, they are expected to be required over larger geographic areas and longer periods of the year. Products and services that inform where the ice is going to be, how closely packed it is and how thick and strong it is, are key information elements for the operator in decision-making when estimating how difficult it will be to go around or through the ice (AMSA Report, 2009).

Depending on accessibility and personal preference or contacts, there is a range of weather and sea ice related apps, e-navigation services and other sources, the route planners can use besides services provided by national meteorological institutes (Lamers et al., 2018). Traditionally, national sea ice and meteorological services have provided information about sea ice conditions as a public service funded by the taxpayers (Knol et al., 2018). Currently the meteorological institute of Norway is responsible for providing WWIC information over a wide area of the Arctic including ocean areas between Norway and Greenland (Jeuring et al., 2020). Also, Russia and Canada have been delegated to forecast and monitor WWIC information (Müller et al., 2023). In the European Arctic the Norwegian and Danish ice charts are used most frequently (Lamers et al., 2018). In the last years, Arctic information has been provided by a more heterogenous community as also the private sector and organizations have become more involved in the service-production chain (Knol et al., 2018). Alongside with this shift, the users of WWIC information have become paying customers. Academic institutions offer ice data as part of ongoing research programs or to support field research campaigns while commercial ice information services provide services that are specific to individual clients with particular needs (AMSA Report, 2009; Haavisto et al., 2020). Haavisto et al. (2020) identified 185 WWIC providers and services in the Arctic (including the Baltic region) of which around half are provided by academic institutions and professional bodies.

2.3 Private and external costs related to shipping

The benefits of sea ice information are concretized specifically through shipping, as this sector is assumably the primary user of such information in the Arctic region and,

therefore, the most relevant beneficiary of such information. This thesis estimates potential partial benefits through avoided fuel and CO₂ costs. To determine the total economic value of a climate service, all benefits must be identified, including financial, environmental, and social gains, regardless of who receives them or where they occur (Anderson et al., 2015). This sub-chapter provides an overview of cost categories related to shipping that might impact the benefit of sea ice information. According to an unpublished questionnaire about the use of sea ice information services the benefits of nowcasting and forecasting sea ice observation data comes from improvements in both safety and optimal routing (Arctic PASSION, 2022).

The economic expenditures of shipping can be divided into private and external costs which together comprise the social costs. Private costs include expenditures such as fuel, capital and maintenance costs that fall to individual shipping operators. External costs are non-internalized costs to society that are not accounted for in the market (Fahlen & Ahlgren, 2010). Shipping externalities refer to the negative impacts or unintended consequences of shipping activities that affect society, the environment, or specific communities. The external and private costs of shipping are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Private and external costs of (Arctic) shipping.

Private costs of shipping	Externalities of shipping	Examples of external costs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fuel • Capital and maintenance • Crew salaries • Insurance • Route fees • Ice breaker assistance tariff • Ice pilot fee • Harbour stays • Rescue costs and other costs related to accidents • Lost revenue caused by accidents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GHG emissions • Air pollution • Underwater noise • Spread of invasive species • Antifouling paint and biofouling on ship hull • Solid waste, ballast water, bilge water, black water, grey water, scrubber wash water, stern tube oil, tank cleaning • Accidents (oil spills, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health damage and premature deaths (continuous exposure to externalities such as air pollution) • Biodiversity loss/extinction of species and disruption of local ecosystems • Impacts on local communities and culture • Deaths and environmental damage (accidents)
Private costs + external costs = Total social costs of shipping		

Private costs of shipping include fuel costs, capital costs, crew costs and operational costs like repairs, maintenance, insurance and administrative costs. Other costs that are not related to ships operating in open waters include port costs like taxes, fees,

discharge operation or demurrage (Grifoll et al., 2018; Toscano et al., 2021) and costs related to accidents like fuel spills (Afenyo et al., 2019). Chen et al. (2023) point out that the economic cost of Arctic navigation is relatively higher than in conventional waters, since cost of ice-class vessels is around 0.5 to 1 time higher and Arctic navigation requiring more special equipment, technical support and ice area insurance. On the other hand, Sarrabezoles et al. (2016) argue that, regarding insurance costs, no dramatic price increases for Arctic shipping have been observed. They suggest that this is due to the experience of most Arctic operators, which indicates that they have gained credibility in the eyes of insurance firms. Consequently, this might not be the case for new shipping operators. Other additional costs in the Arctic include ice braker assistance tariffs (Li et al., 2023a), transit tariffs for sailing along routes such as the NSR (Furuichi & Otsuka, 2015) and ice pilot fees in case the route planner does not have the minimum level of knowledge in navigating in ice-covered waters (Furuichi & Otsuka, 2015). Andersson and Ivehammar (2017) estimate a total cost (including labour cost, fuel cost, emission cost and capital cost) of €29.2 million per day for shipping in the area between south of Frederikshavn in Denmark and Gotenburg in Sweden including the area up to the northernmost part of the bay of Bothania.

Beyond private costs, shipping involves externalities that are not directly covered by the shipping operator themselves. Increasing shipping activity in the Arctic increases environmental challenges associated with ship operations including their impacts on climate change, air quality, and marine biodiversity. Like other transportation modes, ships emit CO₂ and water vapor, nitrogen oxides (NO_x), sulphur dioxide (SO₂), carbon monoxide (CO) and particulate matter such as black carbon which reduce air quality and worsen climate change (AMSA Report, 2009). The majority of GHG emissions from shipping consist of CO₂ which has also the greatest global warming potential (Nunes et al., 2017). Also, black carbon has a significant influence on the retreating of the sea ice including its effects on snow and ice albedo which makes it a particular concern in the Arctic (AMSA Report, 2009). Sulphur dioxide, on the other hand, is observed to cause cooling, warming, acid rain and drought dependent on changing concentrations of its levels: too much SO₂ causes global warming and mass extinctions while too little causes cooling and drought. Currently human activities release an amount of SO₂ into the atmosphere that contributes to global warming and widespread extinction of many species (Ward, 2009).

The marine environment is further impacted by the waste streams related to propulsion and engine operations including bilge water from the machinery spaces, stern tube oil from the lubrication of the propeller shaft, scrubber wash water from exhaust gas cleaning systems for the reduction of emissions of sulphur oxides into the atmosphere, ballast water from maintaining ship stability, biocides used in antifouling paints to prevent hull growth, cooling water as well as tank cleaning residuals (Jalkanen et al., 2021). Waste streams stemming from humans on board consist of food waste, black water (sewage), and water from galleys and showers (grey water) as well as other solid waste (Jalkanen et al., 2021). Additionally, ships introduce alien species to new areas (Afenyo et al., 2019; Dobrzycka-Krahe & Medina-Villar, 2023) and generate noise (Jalkanen et al., 2022) primarily caused by propeller cavitation (Jalkanen, 2018) disrupting local ecosystems. For example, Taylor (2021) argues that the population of the orca has been negatively affected by the underwater noise stemming from commercial vessel traffic, tied to international trade. In the Arctic context key arctic species, such as walrus and narwhal have been identified to be particularly sensitive to ship noise (Huntington, 2023). Jalkanen (2022) reports a significant increase in shipping noise emissions in the Arctic between 2014 and 2020. However, the increase is notable in the Arctic because shipping noise emissions in this pristine region have historically been relatively low (Jalkanen, 2022).

In addition to noise, Inuit have reported that whales such as beluga follow tracks by icebreakers which increases the risk of ice-entrapment mortality events if the open water freezes behind them (Huntington, 2023). In addition, Huntington (2023) underlines that in Arctic areas ice conditions may cause vessels to diverge from established shipping routes to avoid hazards which might, besides possible detours and increased fuel consumption, lead to environmental disturbances in additional areas. Besides environmental externalities, other externalities of shipping include for instance negative health impacts (Nunes et al., 2021), premature deaths (AMSA Report, 2009) and impacts on indigenous and non-indigenous people in the Arctic (Lavengood, 2021; Olsen et al., 2019). Studies show that marine traffic has multiple social and cultural impacts on local people in the Arctic (AMSA, 2009). For indigenous people the marine environment is a source of livelihood: traditional fishing and hunting activities as well as recreation activities are disturbed by the marine traffic (Olsen et al. 2019; Huntington et al., 2023).

3 Evaluation of climate services

This chapter explores the theoretical foundation of the evaluation of climate services beginning with an introduction to the concept of the value of information. In addition, previous relevant economic literature in the context of shipping and climate services is introduced.

3.1 Value of information

The economic benefits of climate services are an example of the concept of value of information (VoI) (Anderson et al., 2015). Unlike for other marketable goods, the value of information increases along the increasing use of it (Ziolkowska, 2018). The consumption of information does not decrease the opportunities for someone else to consume it meaning information is a non-subtractable good. Additionally, information is non-excludable when people cannot be prevented from using it which is usually the case in public free-of-charge climate service information (Birchler & Bütler, 2007).

The value of information is formed when the information product gives value to the users or when the information receiver uses it for the task at hand (Repo, 1987). The economic benefit of meteorological and hydrological services lies in the anticipated improvement of a service-assisted decision compared to the expected result of a decision made without the service (Anderson et al., 2015). For example, in this thesis the value of information equals the cost savings gained through better navigation decisions in shipping. Overall, meteorological, hydrological, and related information can deliver significant benefits to society, impacting individuals, households, organizations, businesses, and governments. By enabling more informed decision-making, climate information helps reduce the impacts of natural hazards, enhance daily safety and convenience, boost business profitability, address public health challenges and poverty, improve productivity, strengthen national economies, protect the environment, and provide a secure basis for future planning (Anderson et al., 2015).

The utility value of a piece of information is hereby “the difference between the expected utility a decision-maker can achieve by choosing the best action conditional on the information received and the expected utility from the action that is best in the

absence of information” (Birchler & Bütler, 2007). Value of Information can be defined as shown in Equation 1.

$$I = \text{utility with information} - \text{utility without information} \quad (1)$$

where parameter I refers to the value of information.

When conducting valuation studies on weather and climate services, it is usually assumed that decisionmakers have some level of prior climate knowledge and that without the updated climate information, the prior knowledge is used (Katz & Lazo, 2012). Consequently, the previous definition can be expanded to state that the value of the climate information is equal to the difference between the benefits when the information is used compared to the benefits when prior knowledge is used.

The magnitude of value of information depends on the stakes, the prior uncertainty, the precision of the information and the degree of risk aversion. These factors together define the value of a piece of information, but their individual impact is not always unambiguous. In general, this means that high stakes can mean both low and high value of information and a risk averse individual does not always want to pay more for information. Risk loving agents delay resolving uncertainty and prefer not rushing to get more information. Risk aversion, on the other hand, refers to the kind of behaviour in which agents prefer to resolve uncertainty sooner rather than later. (Birchler & Bütler, 2007) The amount of benefit is also dependent on the nature of weather and climate related risks, the number and types of users and their capability to actually change behaviour to avoid harm or increase economic output (Anderson et al., 2015).

Another consideration is that while the concept of the value of information is often used to describe the value of information products, most often information systems, this approach has also caused division between researchers. For instance, while Hilton (1981) argues that the value of an information system is directly equivalent to the value of the information it provides, Sassone (1981) argues that there is a clear distinction between information and information products by highlighting that in the presence of competing information delivery systems, the demand for these services does not reflect the demand for the information itself but is also influenced by the offerings of other suppliers (Repo, 1987). However, as Ziolkowska (2018) highlights, accounting the value of information in monetary terms must occur in an indirect way because of the

intangible appearance of information. Information itself has no market but information services, on the other hand, have been marketed and assigned a value.

3.2 Climate service evaluation

The evaluation of weather and climate services is often conducted with techniques that are compatible with cost-benefit analysis (CBA) (see Table 2). The most common methods for evaluation as part of a CBA or otherwise, are contingent valuation, revealed preferences, economic decision modelling, benefit transfer, participatory methods and avoided costs assessments. The selection of the method depends on factors such as the aim of the evaluation, the type of the service considered, the current or intended target group of the service, as well as available data and resources for the evaluation. In general, the benefits of climate services practically always exceed the service costs. In fact, economic studies consistently demonstrate that meteorological and hydrological services provide benefit-cost ratios exceeding one ranging from 2:1 to 36:1. (Anderson et al., 2015) However, if adding components to an already well-developed system, it cannot be assumed that benefits clearly exceed costs (Perrels & Juhanko, 2023).

Table 2. Main types of evaluation approaches of weather and climate services based on Perrels and Juhanko (2023).

Type of evaluation approach	Description
Cost-benefit analysis	Compares total costs and benefits of the project over its lifetime
Cost-effectiveness analysis	Seeks the lowest cost for a given level of effectiveness without evaluating benefits
Financial analysis	Analyses the monetary in- and outflows of a project over time for key actors by type of source, risk levels, and financing cost levels
Economic impact / benefit potential study	Analyses how and to what extent an investment or measure is affecting one or more economic sectors or regions
Market uptake study	Evaluating to what extent a new service will be adopted by both existing users of similar services and new users, based on factors such as user characteristics, barriers to adoption, and the product's performance features
Multi-criteria analysis	Evaluates multiple criteria to help choose the best option among alternatives. It involves scoring each alternative based on relevant criteria and may include weighting those criteria

3.3 Review of previous studies

Although there is a broad literature regarding economic valuation of climate services, research addressing the valuation of sea ice information services and climate services

in the Arctic region remains narrow. This thesis is the first, as far as it is known to the author, to evaluate the benefits of sea ice information across the entire Arctic region. This literature review encompasses economic research on shipping and climate services, focusing on studies from the 21st century, with an emphasis on the last decade.

Sawyer and Dupost (2015) studied the economic value generated using satellite imagery in supporting winter navigation in the Baltic Sea in the period 2004-2014. Satellite imagery significantly supports winter navigation in the Baltic Sea by supporting icebreakers in optimizing routes through ice, reducing time and fuel consumption, and improving arrival time predictability. Sawyer and Dupost showed that replacing helicopters with satellite radar generates an estimated annual economic value of €24–€116 million across Finland and Sweden. It is important to note that their study focused on Finnish and Swedish waters, where icebreakers are primarily used to assist ships. In contrast, this thesis examines non-ice class vessels, and the impact of external assistance has not been taken into account. Nevertheless, Sawyer and Dupost's findings suggest that using satellite imagery leads to nearly €1 million annual fuel cost savings for icebreakers in Finland and Sweden.

From the perspective of lake ice services, Dewulf and Mamais (2022) assessed the economic benefits of a public climate service platform in Finland that provides images of water bodies using Sentinel data. According to their findings the platform generates annual benefits ranging from €6.62 million to €24.82 million. Within the same service platform, Lehtinen (2024) assessed the value of a lake ice information service through an avoided-cost approach, estimating an annual benefit of €408 000 and after adjusting for additional information sources, and revised annual benefit of €99 000.

Leviäkangas and Hautala (2009) showed that the Finnish Meteorological Institute's (FMI) services generate roughly €260–€290 million annual benefits for society. Within the total benefits they estimated the benefit for waterways and marine transportation in Finland to be annually €14–€28 million through reduction in the number of accidents. However, it should be noted that only Finnish waters were included, and the information services evaluated, covered data also beyond ice conditions. For aviation, they calculated the benefit to be annually €46 million in avoided accidents, 4 million in fuel savings and 1 million in avoided environmental damage. For trail transportation they estimated annually a €0.3 million saving through

time savings caused by higher accuracy of train timetables. In an earlier study Leviäkangas et al. (2007) studied the economic benefits of meteorological information services in Finland including all service providers into the calculations and estimated the benefit for maritime transport to range from €30.9 to €48.5 million annually. Additionally, they estimated that the Croatian Hydrological and Meteorological Services generate benefits ranging from €4.3 to €7.9 million annually for Croatia's maritime and inland waterway transportation.

Outside the Arctic and maritime sector climate service valuation studies have been conducted widely. A recent study by Bizo et al. (2024) examined the socioeconomic benefits of climate forecasts for farmers in West Africa showing that the utilization of climate information plays a crucial role in improving farmers' average financial incomes. Considine et al. (2004) used an avoided costs model to calculate the additional value of hurricane forecasts for oil and gas producers in the Gulf of Mexico, finding that a 24-hour and a 48-hour forecast helped avoid costs of approximately USD8.1 million annually. Frei et al. (2014) estimated that meteorological services in Switzerland's road transportation sector could result in avoided expenditures ranging from 65.7 to 79.77 million Swiss francs (approximately €70–€85 million). Von Grünigen et al. (2014) evaluated the avoided fuel and flight deviation costs for airlines utilizing terminal aerodrome forecasts and estimated annual savings of 14 to 22 million USD. Lin et al. (2019) studied the economic value of meteorological information services in Taiwan for agricultural producers using contingent valuation. Their results indicate that the economic value of meteorological information services for agricultural producers ranges from 28.06 million to 45.51 million USD per year. In a later paper, Lin et al. (2021) studied the economic value of meteorological information services for aquaculture in Taiwan using contingent valuation. Their results indicate that the total economic value at the national level ranged from 157 to 209 million NTD per year (approximately €4.5–€6 million).

Besides climate service valuation studies there is scarce literature that examines the economic value of voyage optimization systems. Voyage optimization includes utilizing sea ice and other climate information to aid route planning (Schwartz et al., 2020). The main methodologies used for solving weather routing problems include the isochrone method, dynamic programming, calculus of variations, pathfinding algorithms and heuristics but also artificial intelligence and machine learning applications (Zis et al.,

2020). Although optimization systems do not equal the value of sea ice information, both create value through information that helps ships to plan optimized routes and reduce costs, and are therefore considered relevant in the context of this thesis.

Grifoll et al. (2018) studied the economic benefits of a ship routing system that utilizes wave effect on navigation in Short Sea Shipping between Spanish and Italian ports and showed that during energetic wave episodes, the routing system can save up to 18% of total costs by reducing travel time and its associated impacts, such as fuel consumption, crew expenses, and capital costs, under particular bad weather conditions. Du et al. (2022) studied the economic benefits of an improved three-dimensional dynamic programming algorithm for ship route optimization in ice free waters. By focusing on minimizing fuel oil consumption, their algorithm achieved a 1.39% reduction in fuel consumption and 1.59% increase in economic benefit per voyage for an oil tanker. Andersson and Ivehammar (2017) studied the benefits of dynamic route planning in the Baltic Sea region. In dynamic route planning, modern information technology is employed by Sea Traffic Coordination Centres to assist ships in optimizing their route plans, alongside with considering factors such as ice, weather, and so forth. Anderson and Ivehammar estimated the benefits to be €102 million per year, for each 1% distance that can be reduced. These gains are split between reduced emissions costs, which cover 58%, and the remaining 42% representing private avoided costs of the shipping companies. In an earlier study, Andersson and Ivehammar (2015) studied the benefits of the Sea Traffic Management (STM) concept, in which information is shared using diverse technologies and which also includes route optimisation services. Their results show that by implementing STM, 1% reduction in sailed distance could result in potential savings of €37 million annually in Northern Europe. The estimated cost categories in their study included fuel, labor, capital, emissions, and accident costs.

In addition to the literature presented above, a broad body of research evaluates the competitiveness of Arctic routes compared to alternative southern routes from both economic and environmental perspectives. Despite being approximately 40% shorter than southern alternatives, ice conditions cause uncertainties that reduce the attractiveness of Arctic routes (Lasserre, 2015). Given that sea ice information is assumed to aid vessels in navigating icy conditions, feasibility studies focusing on

Arctic routes are considered relevant to the context of this thesis and therefore introduced here.

While a relative majority of the papers considering the feasibility of Arctic routes conclude that Arctic routes are likely to be profitable, Lasserre (2014) argues that without a strong load factor, they will hardly be feasible. Overall, this body of research highlights the uncertainty surrounding the feasibility of Arctic routes, which largely depends on the chosen parameters and their specific values (Lasserre, 2015). For instance, Furuichi and Otsuka (2015), Lindstad et al. (2016), Li et al. (2023a), Cariou et al. (2021), and Schøyen and Bråthen (2011) suggest that certain Arctic routes are more feasible due to lower costs while others show that Arctic routes are not as feasible as thought or project feasibility only in the future (for example, Wang et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2024; Christensen et al., 2022) when compared to southern alternative routes. However, factors such as the considered routes, observation periods and ship types vary across these studies impacting the results. This body of research also includes climate benefit assessments with varying results. For example, Furuichi and Otsuka (2015) found that CO₂ emissions are lower on the NSR than on the SCR, while Lindstad et al. (2016) argue that the NSR does not provide overall climate benefits, as increased Arctic emissions offset the advantages of shorter voyages, even when cleaner fuels are used.

4 Data

This chapter introduces the data.

4.1 Descriptive statistics

The main dataset used in the analysis is from PAME's Arctic Ship Traffic Data (ASTD) System (ASTD, 2024). The dataset includes quantitative historical information on vessels operating within the Arctic region, with boundaries defined according to PAME (Protection of the Arctic Marine Environment) (see Figure 2a). Thirteen Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs) lie within the boundaries of the PAME Arctic Area Proposal as well as open water areas and the Svalbard fisheries zone. Figure 2b illustrates the sea ice extent for March 2023 within the proposed Arctic area.

Figure 2. 2a) PAME Arctic area proposal. 2b) Sea ice extent in the PAME Arctic area Proposal in March 2023. Area of ocean (grid cell =1 km²) with less than 15 percent sea ice concentration is considered ice-free. Source: PAME, ASTD.

In 2023 the total number of ships operating in the PAME area was 11 543. Between 2013 and 2023, the trend in the number of ships has shown an increase (see Figure 3a). In 2020, around the beginning of the covid-19 pandemic, there was a sharp decline in the number of vessels. However, the trend has been increasing since then, although a small drop can be observed between 2022 and 2023. The number of vessels has increased on average 0.72% per year during the period between 2014–2023. This is significantly lower than the 6% annual increase reported by Müller et al. (2023), which is likely due to differences in the geographical boundaries used to define the Arctic. Besides yearly variation, the number of vessels fluctuates also within the year, with the highest number of ships occurring during the summer months (see Figure 3b). The

variation in the number of vessels is primarily driven by changes in the number of conventional vessels, while the number of ice-class vessels remains relatively constant throughout the year.

Figure 3. 3a) Annual count of vessels from 2014 to 2023 and 3b) Count of ice-class and conventional vessels throughout the representative year (2023) in the PAME Arctic Area Proposal.

Most of the ships sailing in the Arctic are bulk carriers, general cargo ships, fishing vessels as well as ships labelled as “other activities” (see Figure 4a). As seen in Figure 4b, the highest number of ships within a year, can be observed in Russian EEZ, Alaskan EEZ, Canadian EEZ and Norwegian EEZ.

Figure 4. 4a) Count of vessels per ship type and 4b) Count of vessels within EEZs during the representative year (2023) in the PAME Arctic Area Proposal.

The ASTD dataset classifies fuel types into four categories which are distillate marine fuels (MGO/MDO), residual marine fuels, liquefied natural gas (LNG), and battery power. Distillates are lighter, further refined and considered as cleaner alternatives than residual fuels. Residual fuels are leftover components of crude oil separated from upgraded, distilled products, and are heavier than distillates. Heavy fuel oils have some of the highest levels of exhaust emissions among marine fuels, particularly black

carbon (ASTD Data Information Document, 2023; Arctic Council, 2024). Figure 5 illustrates the distribution of vessels using these fuel types, categorized by ice class. Most vessels utilize distillates and residual fuels. Residuals are used the most among vessels with ice class 1A and the least among vessels with ice class 1C. Among conventional vessels, around 60% use residuals.

Figure 5. Share of vessels using different fuel types per ice class. The number in the brackets presents the count of vessels within the corresponding ice class during the representative year (2023) in the PAME Arctic Area Proposal.

Figure 6 represents the development of fuel consumption throughout the representative year. Total fuel consumption per month decreases during the winter season and increases in the summer, corresponding to the retreat of the ice edge and shipping activity. On the other hand, the average fuel consumption per nautical mile increases after the summer months, followed by a decrease after the winter months, which could indicate that fuel efficiency decreases during the winter when the ice emerges. However, the data for April, June, and July deviates slightly from this trend.

Figure 6. Total (left-side axis) and average (per nautical mile) (right-side axis) fuel consumption development throughout the representative year (2023) in the PAME Arctic Area Proposal.

In this analysis, data from 2023 is utilized. The dataset consists of 61 910 observations that represent monthly aggregated information about vessels. The panel structure is uniquely identified by a ship ID and month. Table 3 presents the summary statistics.

Table 3. Summary statistics

Variable	Obs.	Mean	Std. dev.
Fuel consumption per month (m3)	61 909	119.1	303.6
CO ₂ emissions per month (metric ton)	60 596	385.8	977.3
CO emissions per month (metric ton)	60 596	0.9	2.2
Nox emissions per month (metric ton)	60 596	7.6	22.9
SO ₂ emissions per month (metric ton)	60 596	0.6	2.3
Distance sailed per month (nautical mile)	61 901	1320.8	1360.8
Hours sailed per month (h)	61 901	480.9	275.4
Vessel age (years old in 2024)	61 909	24.5	16.8
Volume (gross tonnage)	56 491	14319.4	26634.1

The ASTD data quality is considered “very accurate” as described in PAME’s data information document (2023). The data is based on Automatic Identification System (AIS) which is a maritime navigation safety communications system. Regulation 19 in the International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS) requires that navigational equipment must be installed on all ships of 300 GT (gross tonnage) and larger in international voyages and cargo ships of 500 GT and larger in domestic voyages as well as on all passenger ships regardless of their size. AIS signals provide information such as ship type, position, course, speed and other information related to safety. In ASTD the ships position is recorded every 6 minutes. ASTD only includes signals transmitted by ships that carry an AIS Class A transceiver. This means vessels with Class B transceivers, which provide similar benefits for smaller vessels with lower cost and simpler installation, are not included. Although the quality of AIS data in the ASTD system is considered high, it does not cover 100% of all ship traffic since numerous factors can affect the transmission and receipt of AIS signals. For example, technical failures due to faulty infrastructure, erroneous onboard installation of AIS transceiver, problems with data links and networks, manipulation of AIS signals, data noise as well as satellite coverage limitations must be considered. (ASTD Data Information Document, 2023)

4.2 Fuel and carbon costs

The fuel price data is provided by the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA, 2024). It contains average bunker fuel prices in USD\$ per metric ton for various fuel types across 20 major global bunkering locations, including Busan, Colombo, Durban, Fujairah, Gibraltar, Hong Kong, Houston, Istanbul, Los Angeles/Long Beach, Las Palmas, Mumbai, New York, Panama, Piraeus, Rotterdam, Santos, Shanghai, Singapore, St. Petersburg, and Tokyo. The dataset focuses on three key fuel types: IFO 380, a bunker fuel with a maximum sulphur content of 3.5%; VLSFO, a very low sulphur fuel oil with a maximum sulphur content of 0.5%; and Marine Gas Oil (MGO), a clean and bright distillate fuel with a maximum sulphur content of 1.5%. The used price data spans the years 2020 to 2023. The calculated average fuel price is €599.33, adjusted to 2024 prices using an average annual global consumer price index (World Bank, 2024) and the exchange rate USD/EUR (European Central Bank, 2024). The fuel price ranges from €267.58 to €1 046.43 (see Figure 7). The social avoided costs are quantified using CO₂ costs. The range of variation for EU ETS CO₂ prices for the period 2020–2023 is used as an approximation for the social cost of carbon (SCC) from the Trading Economics (2024) website. On March 16th, 2020, the price of one tonne of carbon dioxide reached its lowest point, at €18.13, adjusted to 2024 prices using the global annual Consumer Price Index (CPI). In contrast, the price peaked at €108.18 on March 6th, 2023, also CPI-adjusted. Over this period, the midrange price of CO₂ per tonne was €63.15. During the previous four years, the prices were much lower ranging from around €3 to €30.

Figure 7. Average bunker fuel prices in 2020–2023 including IFO 380, VLSFO and MGO. Source: USDA 2024/Ship&Bunker. Prices have been CPI-adjusted by the author afterwards.

The average fuel and CO₂ prices have been adjusted to 2024 prices using the average global Consumer Price Index (CPI) from the World Bank for the period 2014–2023. The global CPI was selected due to the international nature of the shipping industry. On average, prices have increased by 3.136% annually during this period (World Bank, 2024). The analysis utilizes the average exchange rate of 0.9214 for US dollars to Euros, as reported by the European Central Bank (2024) for the period between January and November 2024.

4.3 Service costs

To be able to compare the benefits and costs of sea ice information, the costs of a representative sea ice service is used. The service considered, currently in development stage, aims to develop an operational service to better quantify the risk to a vessel as it navigates through ice-covered waters. As a new feature, the service aims to improve the POLARIS risk assessment methodology by analysing historical ship traffic coincident sea ice conditions and extending the current method to add a forecasting capability. The POLARIS methodology will provide a risk index outcome (RIO) score in near real time to estimate the operational limitations of ships within the local ice conditions corresponding to their ice class. When mature, the service will produce predicted forecasts hours to days and weeks to months beforehand. (Arctic PASSION, 2024)

The cost of the pilot-phase sea ice service, developed in the Arctic PASSION project, includes personnel costs, costs of equipment and infrastructure as well as costs associated with data processing and service provision. Expenses related to the personnel, include wages, salaries, and obligatory social security charges. Annual maintenance cost of the service, asked directly from the service developer, is approximately €36 500. In the development stage, the annual cost is €86 500. (Arctic PASSION, 2024)

5 Methods

This chapter presents the methodology, discusses the associated challenges, and outlines the key assumptions underlying the analysis.

5.1 Avoided costs framework

The evaluation in this thesis is based on a benefit potential study as defined in Perrels and Juhanko (2023). The approach focuses on analysing how and to what extent an investment or measure (in this context, the implementation of a sea ice service) is affecting one or more economic sectors (here the shipping sector). A benefit study provides building blocks for a complete Cost-benefit Analysis or Cost-effectiveness Analysis (Perrels et al., 2013). As a valuation method, the avoided cost framework is used. Avoided costs assessments are based on the idea that in order to value a new weather service, the benefits of the service are compared to non-use or use of older version of the service (Perrels & Juhanko, 2023). In other words, the avoided or saved cost after implementation of the service is, in fact, the benefit of the service. The service evaluated in this analysis is assumed to provide information about ice extent and its associated risks to the vessel, and to function as an add-on service, complementing the existing services.

According to standard economic theory, value of information is based on its ability to improve decisions making. In shipping, ice information helps route planners to plan their routes better which assumably shortens shipping distance and/or reduces power usage in icy waters. The route shortens as route planners know where the ice is and how risky and challenging it is to access certain areas with the corresponding ice class of the vessel. With this information ships also avoid getting stuck in ice or in case of facing inaccessible ice, avoid having to turn around and find a better route. Less power is needed when route planners can avoid areas in which more power is needed to get through (high resistance of ice) which means that costs can still be avoided, although the distance gets longer. Here the assumption is that the information about ice, makes it possible for route planners to find a shorter or more easily accessible route than without the information. In the valuation technique the savings in operating costs are assumed to equal the benefits i.e. the avoided costs that stem from avoided fuel and CO₂ emission costs the information provides (see illustration in Figure 8). In other

words, the benefits equal the value of information as presented in equation 1 in chapter 3.1.

Figure 8. Simplified illustration of vessel's optimized route with sea ice information (blue) compared to the route without sea ice information (red) with detours and additional power usage (zigzag pattern). The vessel sails towards the x-mark. Note: Going through the ice is either impossible or entails an increase in fuel consumption because of increased resistance of ice.

The total avoided fuel costs are calculated using the following equation:

$$AF = [(FP \times FC_1 \times TA) + (FP \times FC_2 \times TA) + \dots + (FP \times FC_n \times TA)] \times ADOP \times ACC \quad (2)$$

Where AF refers to the total avoided fuel costs. The right side of the equation sums up the avoided fuel costs from all vessels (1 to n vessels) that use the service. The factor FP refers to the fuel price whereas FC refers to the fuel consumption in cubic meters. The factor TA refers to the share (%) of the total fuel consumption which can be avoided through sea ice information. The factors $ADOP$ and ACC refer to the adoption of the service i.e. to the share (%) of the vessels that use the service and to the accuracy of the service.

The total avoided CO₂ costs are calculated using the following equation:

$$AC = [(CP \times CC_1 \times TA) + (CP \times CC_2 \times TA) + \dots + (CP \times CC_n \times TA)] \times ADOP \times ACC \quad (3)$$

Where AC refers to the total avoided CO₂ costs. The right side of the equation sums up the avoided CO₂ costs from all vessels (1 to n vessels) that use the service. The factor CP refers to the tCO₂ price whereas CC refers to CO₂ emissions in metric ton. The factor TA refers to the share (%) of the total CO₂ emissions that can be avoided through sea ice information. As above, the factors $ADOP$ and ACC refer to the adoption of the

service i.e. to the share (%) of the vessels that use the service and to the accuracy of the service.

The benefits of climate services will vary in magnitude over time. The benefits of new climate services tend to increase over time because of the learning curve or lagged adoption. This is caused by the fact that it takes time for users to build trust for the service and make the best choices corresponding the information from it (Anderson et al., 2015). Also, the specific realized conditions in the observed year affect the value. For example, in a year with challenging ice conditions the value of a sea ice information may be higher than on years with less challenging sea ice conditions. For calculating the present value (PV) for benefits, Equation 4 is used:

$$PV \text{ benefits} = \sum \frac{AF}{(1+r)^t} \quad (4)$$

Where *PV benefits* refer to the total benefits of the service over the observed time frame. On the right side of the equation *AF* refers to the total avoided fuel costs (or respectively *AC* for total avoided CO₂ costs) in the specific year *t* and *r* is the discount rate. A sensitivity analyses with 1%, 3% and 7% discount rates are conducted.

For calculating the present value for costs, Equation 5 is used:

$$PV \text{ costs} = \sum \frac{C_t}{(1+r)^t} \quad (5)$$

Where *PV costs* represent the total costs of the service over the observed time frame. On the right-hand side of the equation *C_t* refers to the total costs for the specific year *t* and *r* represents the discount rate. The net present value (NPV) is calculated by subtracting the net present costs from the net present benefits. However, due to estimating only partial benefits, the total NPV cannot be estimated in this analysis.

5.2 Assumptions and uncertainty

The following base values are set for key variables (see Table 4), with their underlying assumptions detailed next. Table 4 also presents the value ranges used in the sensitivity analyses.

Table 4. Base values for key variables.

Key variable	Base value	MC Simulation or basic sensitivity analysis
Fuel price (€/m ³)	€599.33	€267.58 – €1046.43 (Uniform distribution)

Key variable	Base value	MC Simulation or basic sensitivity analysis
CO ₂ price (€/tCO ₂)	€63.15	€18.13 – €108.18 (Uniform distribution)
Service accuracy (%)	90%	85–95% (Uniform distribution)
Service adoption (users of all considered vessels, %)	10%	0.1%, 1%, 10%, 100%

Many studies assume a 100% accuracy of the service meaning that the forecasts are perfect. The accuracy of climate information refers to the degree to which the information reflects the actual climatic conditions. However, the benefits are highly dependent on the conditions that occur compared to those conditions from the perfect forecast scenario. Therefore, no valuation study should claim to determine the value of "perfect information," but it can consider it as a potential upper bound for the value of the information. The accuracy of warnings about sea ice conditions often depends on the skill of those responsible for forecasting these conditions (Anderson et al., 2015). Mironov et al. (2021) study the sea ice forecast accuracy by analysing sea ice processes in autumn 2021 in the Russian Arctic Seas. They show that the overall accuracy of long-term ice forecasts was 75% whereas the accuracy of short-term forecast of ice conditions varied between 85% and 95%. The accuracy of temperature forecasts within a 24-hour timeframe, provided by the FMI, is 90% (FMI, 2024). This thesis assumes a baseline accuracy of sea ice forecast to be 90% and conducts a sensitivity analysis to assess how changes in accuracy change the estimates.

In particularly when considering new services, also the rate of adoption of the new service may require assumptions, although typically the rate of adoption is expected to increase over time. In some instances, adoption rates may approach 100% (e.g., households using weather forecasts). However, for many sector-specific services, adoption tends to be lower due to challenges in communicating services or limited opportunities for users to act on improved or new meteorological and hydrological information. Factors that may impact the behaviour of potential users and the rate of adoption of the service include 1) How well the service is communicated to the user; 2) Characteristics of the service (for example, accuracy); 3) Decisionmaker characteristics (for example, risk aversion, or prior knowledge of information); 4) Decisionmaker environment (for example, government programmes and policies that might affect adoption of services); and 5) Availability of resources and management options for changing behaviour in response to information. (Anderson et al., 2015) Conducting a

sensitivity analysis helps assessing the impact of these factors. This analysis assumes the base adoption rate to be 10% of the analysed vessels since the representative sea ice service is assumed to be an additional supporting service to the existing ones. However, a sensitivity analysis is conducted to see how avoided costs change if the share of users who benefit from the information is changed.

In addition, it is challenging to predict how people and businesses will respond to forecasts in any given year. In this analysis, this uncertainty translates to difficulty in estimating the extent to which sea ice information will reduce fuel consumption or emissions by vessels. Some ships may not reduce their fuel consumption at all while other ships may reduce it by several percentage points. Therefore, the results are presented as avoided costs per 1% reduction in fuel consumption or, correspondingly, in CO₂ emissions over a given time frame.

This thesis conducts both a basic sensitivity analysis when one variable changes at a time and a Monte Carlo (MC) simulation to examine the range of outcomes when multiple variables vary simultaneously. MC Simulation is particularly effective in scenarios where multiple sources of uncertainty or variability influence the estimates. The approach involves selecting a large set of random initial positions and using numerical simulations to observe how a system evolves (Black et al., 2017).

5.3 Study setting

In the analysis all conventional vessels without an ice class inside the PAME's Arctic area proposal during 2023 are considered since they are assumed to primarily benefit from sea ice information. Also, fishing vessels are excluded from the analysis since they are assumed to choose routes without the aim of minimizing route distance. Fishing vessels are assumed to spend time seeking and catching fish rather than simply sail and minimize distance. Research vessels, similarly, may follow specific patterns in an area or stay in one location to take measurements, but this is not considered in this thesis since the dataset does not segregate specifically research vessels.

Firstly, avoided costs are calculated for the whole year and then for the winter season from the beginning of November until the end of April since the Arctic's ice extent begins to increase around October and the ice edge retreats again around May (ASTD, 2024). The aim is to get an overall picture about how much costs can be avoided in the

Arctic as a whole. During the winter season, there is a greater extent of ice coverage; however, certain regions become inaccessible. In contrast, during the summer season, some areas may be ice-free, while others remain covered with ice and floating ice threatens ships. In addition, climate change increases dynamic and uncertain ice conditions that vary annually.

Secondly, the differences in avoided costs between ship types are calculated. The benefits are calculated for winter months (January, February and March) which is the time of year with the greatest ice extent. Thirdly, differences in avoided costs are studied by observing how the benefit varies between Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs). The EEZs differ among other things in size, ice conditions and shipping activity. In the EEZ-level analysis the 3-months period from January to March is used. The goal is to assess to which extent different ship types and regions could benefit from ice information during the winter months.

In total 7 287 vessels without an ice class sail in the Arctic during the representative year (2023) when fishing vessels are excluded. These vessels' fuel costs sum up to around €3.1 billion per year and the CO₂ costs sum up to around €252 million per year. The total fuel costs of the 5 214 vessels sailing in the Arctic during the 6-month period (January, February, March, April, November and/or December) in 2023 are approximately €1.3 billion whereas the total CO₂ costs are approximately €430 million.

6 Results

This chapter presents the result of the avoided cost analysis. Additionally, the results of the sensitivity analyses and Monte Carlo simulations are presented. The future benefit of sea ice information is evaluated through present value calculations using scenarios. Finally, the partial benefits are compared to the costs of a representative sea ice service.

6.1 Avoided fuel and CO₂ costs

Every additional 1% avoided in total fuel consumption saves €2.8 million in fuel costs per year. The corresponding savings in CO₂ costs are €940 000 per year. Over the six-month period (November to April), each additional 1% reduction in total fuel consumption results in savings of €1.2 million in fuel costs and €390 000 in CO₂ costs per winter season.

The ship type-level analysis, conducted for the winter months (January, February, and March) show that bulk carriers achieve the greatest savings, with every 1% reduction in fuel consumption translating to €105 000 in fuel cost savings and €35 000 in CO₂ cost savings (see Table 5). The EEZ-level analysis conducted for the winter months (January, February, and March), indicates greatest savings in fuel and CO₂ costs within the Alaskan and Norwegian EEZ (see Table 6).

Table 5. Avoided fuel and CO₂ costs by ship type, €/1% avoided in total fuel consumption during winter months (January–February–March).

Ship type	Avoided fuel cost, €	Avoided CO ₂ cost, €	Avoided emissions, tCO ₂ (MGO/MDO)	Avoided emissions, tCO ₂ (residuals)	Avoided emissions, tCO ₂ (LNG /battery power)
Bulk carriers	105 098	35 221	13	543	1
Chemical tankers	26 360	8 818	15	109	16
Container ships	97 909	32 837	14	503	2
Crude oil tankers	39 741	13 346	42	156	13
Gas tankers	99 813	33 570	0	531	0
General cargo ships	53 333	17 680	4	268	7
Oil product tankers	5 517	1 749	4	24	0
Refrigerated cargo ships	7 196	2 353	1	36	0
Roro cargo ships	31 074	10 439	2	96	67
Cruise ships	12 517	4 201	7	51	8

Ship type	Avoided fuel cost, €	Avoided CO ₂ cost, €	Avoided emissions, tCO ₂ (MGO/MDO)	Avoided emissions, tCO ₂ (residuals)	Avoided emissions, tCO ₂ (LNG /battery power)
Offshore supply ships	14 838	4 983	70	2	7
Other activities	84 694	28 096	349	88	8
Other service offshore ships	8 311	2 594	20	21	0
Passenger ships	70 891	23 769	85	199	93
In total	657 292	219 656	626	2 627	222

Table 6. Avoided fuel and CO₂ costs by EEZ, €/1% avoided in total fuel consumption during winter months (January–February–March).

Area	Avoided fuel cost, €	Avoided CO ₂ cost, €	Avoided emissions, tCO ₂
Alaskan EEZ	120 384	40 282	638
Canadian EEZ	75 783	25 258	400
Faeroe islands EEZ	6 354	2 133	34
Finnish EEZ	8 991	2 968	47
Greenlandic EEZ	648	215	3
Icelandic EEZ	4 076	1 362	22
Jan Mayen EEZ	0	0	0
Norwegian EEZ	115 211	38 394	608
Open Waters Arctic	14	5	0
Open waters Barents Sea	1 424	480	8
Open waters Bering Sea EEZ	345	116	2
Open waters Davis Strait	0	0	0
Open waters North Atlantic	0	0	0
Open waters Norwegian Sea EEZ	230	77	1
Russian EEZ	111 890	37 504	594
Svalbard Fisheries Zone	2 065	693	11
Swedish EEZ	1 372	455	7
United Kingdom EEZ	26	9	0
United States EEZ	41 113	13 740	240
In total	489 926	163 691	2 615

Based on the proximity to the major shipping routes (Northern Sea Route (NSR) and the Northwest Passage (NWP)) as well as on the levels of shipping activity, measured by the number of individual vessels sailing these regions, the avoided costs are calculated for four ship types in four areas. The results indicate that largest savings in

fuel and CO₂ costs can be reached in the Alaskan EEZ by container ships (see Tables 7 and 8).

Table 7. Avoided fuel costs in major EEZs by ship type, €/1% avoided in total fuel consumption during winter months (January–February–March).

	Bulk carriers	Container ships	General cargo ships	RoRo ships	Chemical tankers
Alaskan EEZ	42 500	43 221	3 744	8 275	2 667
Canadian EEZ	23 852	19 300	2 438	6 498	1 703
Norwegian EEZ	10 800	896	4 541	342	2013
Russian EEZ	10 083	7 584	6 548	648	859

Table 8. Avoided CO₂ costs in major EEZs by ship type, €/1% avoided in total CO₂ emissions during winter months (January–February–March).

	Bulk carriers	Container ships	General cargo ships	RoRo ships	Chemical tankers
Alaskan EEZ	14 241	14 524	1 250	2 786	897
Canadian EEZ	7 975	6 454	813	2 182	572
Norwegian EEZ	3 633	299	1 511	114	673
Russian EEZ	3 374	2 549	2 185	218	288

6.2 Sensitivity analysis

A sensitivity analysis was conducted to address uncertainty in service adoption, using adoption rates of 0.1%, 1%, 10%, and 100%. These rates represent the proportion of potential users benefiting from sea ice information. Other variables are kept fixed. The analysis was performed for both 12-month and 6-month time frames (see Table 9).

Table 9. Avoided fuel and CO₂ costs, €/1% avoided in total fuel consumption in the 12-month period (January to December) and in the 6-month period (January, February, March, April, November and/or December).

	0.1% users	1% users	10% users	100% users
Avoided fuel costs (12-month)	28 104	281 040	2 810 403	28 104 034
Avoided CO ₂ costs (12-month)	9 401	94 014	940 136	9 401 356
Avoided fuel costs (6-month)	11 566	115 659	1 156 592	11 565 922
Avoided CO ₂ costs (6-month)	3 867	38 673	386 735	3 867 349

6.3 Monte Carlo Simulations

A Monte Carlo (MC) simulation was performed to evaluate the sensitivity associated with price variability and information accuracy. Service adoption is excluded from the Monte Carlo Analysis because it is assumed to have a dominant influence on the distribution and consequently, it is analysed separately through the basic sensitivity analysis (see Chapter 6.2). The MC simulation comprised 1 000 iterations, during which key variables were varied within the ranges specified in Chapter 5.2 (Table 4). The weights of the ranges were distributed according to a uniform distribution. Table 10 shows the Monte Carlo summary statistics.

Table 10. Monte Carlo summary statistics (1 000 iterations). Avoided fuel and CO₂ costs, €/1% avoided in total fuel consumption.

	Avoided fuel costs, 12-month period, €	Avoided fuel costs, 6-month period, €	Avoided CO ₂ costs, 12-month period, €	Avoided CO ₂ costs, 6-month period, €
Mean	3 120 874	1 255 849	932 878	391 138
Minimum	1 200 489	492 117	257 919	111 270
Maximum	5 113 764	2 085 590	1 673 115	692 821
Standard deviation	1 070 761	443 417	392 349	165 129

Figures 9a and 9b show the distribution of occurrences by 10% percentiles derived from the Monte Carlo analysis of avoided fuel and CO₂ costs over the 12-month period. Similarly, Figures 10a and 10b illustrate the corresponding distributions for the 6-month period.

Figure 9. Distribution of occurrences by 10% percentiles derived from the Monte Carlo simulation of avoided fuel (9a) and CO₂ (9b) costs for every additional 1% avoided in total fuel consumption in the 12-month period.

Figure 10. Distribution of occurrences by 10% percentiles derived from the Monte Carlo simulation of avoided fuel (10a) and CO₂ (10b) costs for every additional 1% avoided in total fuel consumption in the 6-month period.

Figure 11a presents the Monte Carlo distribution of avoided fuel costs per ship type during the 3-month winter period from January to March, while Figure 11b shows the corresponding avoided CO₂ costs, both influenced by variations in fuel and CO₂ prices as well as service accuracy.

Figure 11. Avoided fuel costs (11a) and avoided CO₂ costs (11b) for every additional 1% avoided in total fuel consumption in January, February and March (2023). The solid boxes represent the interquartile range (middle 50% of the data) for each set of observations, with the median value shown as a horizontal line inside the box and the mean value as a cross (x). Whiskers show the upper and lower quartile of observations.

Figure 12 presents the Monte Carlo distribution of avoided fuel and CO₂ costs across major EEZs during the 3-month winter period from January to March, influenced by variations in fuel and CO₂ prices as well as service accuracy.

Figure 12. Avoided fuel costs (12a) and CO₂ costs (12b) for every additional 1% avoided in total fuel consumption in January, February and March (2023). The solid boxes represent the interquartile range (middle 50% of the data) for each set of observations, with the median value shown as a horizontal line inside the box and the mean value as a cross (x). Whiskers show the upper and lower quartile of observations.

6.4 Scenario based present value calculations

To evaluate the future benefits of sea ice information, the present value (PV) of benefits is calculated for the period 2024–2100 under three scenarios, reflecting different assumptions about future trends.

- **Scenario 1:** In the first scenario, it is assumed that benefits will grow by 0.72% annually, consistent with the observed 0.72% annual increase in the number of ships in the study area between 2014 and 2023.
- **Scenario 2:** The second scenario assumes that benefits remain constant throughout the period.
- **Scenario 3:** The third scenario considers the potential impact of diminishing sea ice, as the Arctic Ocean is projected to experience ice-free summers as early as 2040 or 2050, while the annual freezing and melting cycle persists (AMSA Report, 2009). This scenario assumes that benefits will gradually decrease each year, halving by 2100 compared to 2024 (arbitrarily assigned), to account for the reduced need for sea ice navigation services in an increasingly ice-free Arctic.

The development of benefits (avoided costs) is presented in Figure 13 over time from 2024 to 2100 (not discounted). As initial benefit, the avoided cost from the entire Arctic in the 12-month period is used. It should be noted that the 76-year timeframe may not reflect the lifespan of a specific sea ice service.

Figure 13. 13a) Avoided fuel cost and 13b) Avoided CO₂ cost for every additional 1% avoided in total fuel consumption when sea ice information value changes between 2024–2100. (Not discounted) In scenario 1, the benefits increase, in scenario 2, the benefits remain constant and in scenario 3, the benefits decrease over time, as described above.

Tables 11 and 12 present the present value (PV) of benefits from 2024 to 2100 across various scenarios, while also evaluating the sensitivity of these values to changes in the annual discount rate.

Table 11. Present value of the benefits through avoided fuel costs per 1% avoided fuel consumption

Discount rate	PV for scenario 1, €	PV for scenario 2, €	PV for scenario 3, €
3%	101 270 650	84 059 981	68 257 094
1%	193 174 356	150 416 371	113 382 540
7%	44 326 863	39 929 279	35 443 039

Table 12. Present value of the benefits through avoided CO₂ costs per 1% avoided CO₂ emissions

Discount rate	PV for scenario 1, €	PV for scenario 2, €	PV for scenario 3, €
3%	33 877 036	28 119 727	22 833 349
1%	64 620 644	50 317 252	37 928 703
7%	14 828 213	13 357 134	11 856 398

6.5 Cost development

Annual maintenance cost of the Arctic PASSION PS6 service, is approximately €36 500 and if development costs are included, the annual cost increases to €86 500 (Arctic PASSION, 2024). Assuming that the development costs are included in the first five years from 2024 to 2028, followed by only maintenance costs until 2100, the present value of costs at a 3% discount rate is approximately €1.3 million. With an

adoption rate of 10% the present value of benefits, which is counted in tens of millions, significantly exceeds the present value of costs, even when accounting only for partial benefits gained through avoided fuel and CO₂ costs (See Table 13). The present value of benefits, shown in Table 13, represent a range of the benefits generated through avoided fuel and CO₂ costs for each 1% reduction in total fuel consumption. All scenarios presented in Chapter 6.4 are included into the range of benefits.

Table 13. Comparing the present value of costs and partial present value of benefits gained through avoided fuel and CO₂ costs in the time frame 2024–2100. All scenarios presented in Chapter 6.4. are included into the range of benefits.

Discount rate	PV of costs, €	PV of benefits (10% adoption rate), €	PV of benefits (0.1% adoption rate), €
3%	1 320 711	53 286 413 – 200 733 623	532 864 – 2 007 336
1%	2 196 198	59 155 075 – 257 795 000	591 550 – 2 577 950
7%	723 590	47 299 437 – 151 311 243	472 994 – 1 513 112

7 Discussion

7.1 Avoided costs

The main results of this thesis show that every additional 1% avoided in total fuel consumption by vessels in the Arctic saves annually €2.8 million in fuel costs and €940 000 in CO₂ costs. In the analysis covering the 6-month period (November to April), each additional 1% reduction in total fuel consumption results in savings of €1.2 million in fuel costs and €390 000 in CO₂ costs per winter. Both results indicate significant benefits compared to the costs of the service which are €86 500 annually when development costs are included and 36 500 when the service is mature. However, it is important to note that the satellite infrastructure is assumed to be pre-existing, and its associated costs are not included which might transfer to underestimated service costs. In addition, the development costs cover only those expenses incurred during the project, and any costs related to the work of developing the methodological aspects prior to the project are not included. It should also be noted that an adoption rate of 10% is assumed for the service in these numbers. When using the 12-month period results and the adoption rate of 0.1% the avoided fuel costs sum up to €28 000 annually and the avoided CO₂ costs to €9 400 annually per 1% of avoided fuel consumption. Using these numbers, it would require nearly a 2.5% reduction in fuel consumption to reach a point where the avoided CO₂ costs and avoided fuel costs cover annual costs of the service (with development costs). However, avoided fuel and CO₂ costs are not the only sources of benefits, which indicates that the total benefits actually exceed the costs with less effort.

When analysing the avoided costs by ship type during the 3-month winter period (January, February, and March), the results show that bulk carriers achieve the greatest savings, with every 1% reduction in fuel consumption translating to €105 000 in fuel cost savings and €35 000 in CO₂ cost savings. Bulk carriers cover the highest share of ships sailing in the Arctic and non-ice class bulk carriers emit the most CO₂ during the winter period. The results indicate that for most ship types the avoided CO₂ costs are generated primarily through reductions in the consumption of residual fuels. Only for ships that fall into the category of “other activities” and offshore supply ships the avoided CO₂ costs are generated primarily through reductions in distillate marine fuels (MGO/MDO).

Further, the results show greatest savings in fuel and CO₂ costs within the Alaskan and Norwegian EEZ during the 3-month winter period. In the Alaskan EEZ, every 1% reduction in fuel consumption translates to €120 000 in fuel cost savings and €40 000 in CO₂ cost savings. There is no traffic and consequently no avoided costs within the Open waters North Atlantic, Open waters Davis Strait and Jan Mayen EEZ during the 3-month winter period. In addition, within the EEZs largest savings in fuel and CO₂ costs can be reached in the Alaskan EEZ by container ships which generate avoided fuel costs of €43 000 and avoided CO₂ costs of €14 000 for every additional 1% avoided in fuel consumption. It should be noted that the results from the analysis considering the EEZs present avoided costs only at EEZ-level and whether ships sail through multiple EEZs is not considered. Put differently, if a ship sails through multiple EEZ, the 1% reduction in fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions are considered to take place in all these EEZ separately. Another matter to point out is that all EEZs are not fully covered, since just the area that fits within the borders of PAME Arctic Area Proposal is considered. For example, a large part of the United Kingdom EEZ locates outside this area.

As discussed in Chapter 2.3, the total value of sea ice information consists of multiple benefits that are not all covered in this analysis (See Table 1 in Chapter 2.3). According to Grifoll et al. (2018) who analysed a typical Short Sea Shipping (SSS) vessel, capital costs account for over 50% of the total shipping costs, while fuel costs represent approximately 25%. However, their analysis included only capital costs, fuels costs, crew costs and costs regarding repairs, maintenance, insurance, and administrative costs meaning that for example port costs, possible accident costs and externalities were excluded. Leviäkangas and Hautala (2009) showed that the services provided by the FMI (Finnish Meteorological Institute) can save annually €14–€28 million in accident costs related to waterways and marine transportation in Finland. These results indicate that the benefits calculated in this analysis cover only a fraction of the potential benefits of sea ice information.

Andersson and Ivehammar (2015) showed that each 1% reduced in sailed distance could result in potential savings of €37 million annually in Northern Europe. In a later study Anderson and Ivehammar (2017) indicated that each 1% reduced in sailed distance could result in potential savings of €102.4 million in the Baltic region. Their results show significantly greater benefits compared to those observed in this analysis.

However, it is important to note that Andersson and Ivehammar employed a higher price for emissions and incorporated additional cost categories into their analysis. Furthermore, their study focused on different geographical area that vary in shipping activity levels and ice conditions.

7.2 Results robustness

As shown by the results, the implementation of a sea ice service can be highly beneficial across the Arctic. However, the valuation is challenging because the value-creation process is both dynamic and interactive causing uncertainties (Anderson et al., 2015). Environmental cost and benefit functions tend to be highly nonlinear, unlike in this study. Usually, the damage caused by GHG emissions does not increase linearly with the level of emissions but rather increase quickly after some threshold is reached (Pindyck, 2007). In this study it was assumed that every additional tCO₂ was at the same cost.

Also, the number of users benefiting from sea ice information remains highly uncertain. It can be assumed that all vessels operating in the Arctic rely on sea ice information to some extent, suggesting that the benefits could be calculated based on an adoption rate of around 100%. However, when focusing on the benefits provided by an individual ice information provider, the adoption rate decreases due to the high and growing number of service providers and already existing knowledge. In the sensitivity analysis the avoided costs are calculated assuming adoption rates of 0.1%, 1%, 10% and 100%. For example, in the 12-month period fuel costs can be avoided by €28 000 annually if assuming an adoption rate of 0.1%. However, when assuming a 100% adoption rate the, the avoided fuel costs sum up to €28 million annually.

The EU ETS carbon price was used as an approximation for the social cost of carbon (SCC). The EU ETS carbon price serves as a lower-bound estimate since it fails to account for the full SCC i.e. the economic cost caused by an additional ton of carbon dioxide emissions (Nordhaus, 2017), which is generally much higher. This pricing approach may underestimate the true cost of carbon emission, leading to an underestimation of the benefits calculated in this analysis. It should also be noted that the CO₂ price significantly depends on the chosen time frame. It has been estimated that to fully decarbonize international shipping by 2050, the average carbon price

would need to be around \$191/tCO₂ and reach a maximum of around \$358/tCO₂ (Dominioni et al., 2022).

The fuel price data was based on fuel prices in 20 major ports in the world. Applying non-Arctic data risks misrepresenting the realities of fuel usage in this area. However, using fuel prices from around the world is assumed suitable because of the international nature of the shipping industry. Furthermore, the analysis relies on the average prices of three fuel types without weighting them according to their actual distribution or considering specialized fuels required for arctic low-temperature conditions. Fuels that are for low temperatures, might come at a higher price (Lasserre, 2015). It should be also noted that the fuel price data is drawn from the period encompassing the COVID-19 pandemic and the ongoing war in Ukraine, both of which have caused unprecedented volatility in global energy markets and influenced fuel prices in ways that do not accurately reflect long-term trends or the typical economic conditions (Martínez-García et al., 2023; Sakib et al., 2023).

Assessing the accuracy of the sea ice information is challenging as it depends on the benchmark for "perfect" information and the extent to which biases in ice data are acceptable. In addition, ice information is dependent on other climate data which affects the accuracy of ice information (Wei et al., 2023). In this analysis, the accuracy was based on a study by Mironov et al. (2021), conducted in the Russian Arctic under autumn conditions, which is not comprehensive.

Fuel and CO₂ prices, as well as the service accuracy are included in the Monte Carlo analysis which shows the distribution of avoided costs generated by every additional 1% avoided in fuel consumption as these key variables change. The avoided fuel costs in the 12-month period vary between €1.2 million and €5.1 million whereas avoided CO₂ costs between €260 000 and €1.7 million. In the 6-month period avoided fuel costs vary between €490 000 and €2.1 million whereas avoided CO₂ costs between €110 000 and €690 000. These results show that prices along with service accuracy have a great impact on the benefits. Figures 9 and 10, which present the distribution of occurrences by 10% percentiles, show that the number of occurrences varies between approximately 40 and 120 across the percentiles when considering avoided fuel and CO₂ costs for both the 6-month and 12-month periods.

A further uncertainty of this analysis considers the magnitude of fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions that can actually be avoided. This thesis presents avoided costs as a linear benefit function, quantifying the benefits generated by each additional 1% reduction in fuel consumption to address this challenge. However, the level of avoidance varies between voyages. Du et al. (2022) show that an oil tanker achieves 1.39% reduction in fuel consumption and 1.59% increase in economic benefit per voyage through dynamic route planning algorithm in ice free waters. Forsman and Andersson (2015) show that in one month in the Sea of Kattegat, it is possible to reduce fuel consumption with 10.9% by optimising routes using STM (Sea Traffic Management). Mussells et al. (2017) provide an example from the Hudson Strait in the Canadian archipelago where vessels become beset for hours to days at a time. The average distance the MV Arctic (the studied vessel) travelled in the Hudson Strait, during the studied time period, was 625 km. However, the distance might increase if the vessel turns around because of ice or risk of besetment and looks for a better route. According to Mussells et al. during the study period the ship was beset 9–66% of the full transit time and the distance ranged from 561 km to 872 km. The difference between the maximum and minimum distance is hereby 311 km indicating that the actual saving in distance and fuel consumption can vary significantly between transits. These examples show that there is potential for shorter routes as well as fuel and emission savings at varying levels in both ice-free and icy waters.

Other uncertainties to be considered, are related to predetermined routes, ice breaker assistance and lack of ice in some parts of the study area. According to a personal communication with a sea ice expert from the Finnish Meteorological institute (personal communication, October 15, 2024), the potential benefits that can be gained through route optimizing, are narrow in Finland's seas because ships in Finland tend to use predetermined routes and are always assisted by ice breakers when there is ice which makes sea ice information less relevant for optimizing routes. As outlined by the expert, the need for ice breaker assistance is not likely to decrease through milder winters as ice conditions are becoming more unpredictable and dynamic.

According to another personal communication with a marine researcher from the Finnish Meteorological Institute (personal communication, November 5, 2024) the most southern sea areas across the PAME Arctic Area Proposal, including the Norwegian, Greenlandic and Baltic seas, will not benefit from route optimizing because

of lack of ice and because potential route optimizing benefits are narrow. These two statements about the southern regions, specifically, 1) the lack of sea ice in the southern part of the study area (PAME Arctic Area Proposal) and 2) the limited opportunities for route optimization by using sea ice information, indicate that the results of this analysis for the entire area, including the southern regions, particularly over the 12-month period, might represent an overestimation of the potential avoided costs.

Additionally, this analysis excludes ice-class vessels and fishing vessels. Ice-class vessels cover about 25% and fishing vessels about 15% of all vessels in the study area in 2023 (the shares overlap). Sawyer and Dupost (2015) show that the use of satellite imagery in winter navigation results in nearly €1 million in annual fuel cost savings for icebreakers in Finland and Sweden, indicating the benefits of ice information for ice breakers. However, these vessels are omitted from the analysis because risk-related information is particularly valuable for less capable vessels with lower polar classifications, as indicated in Arctic PASSION (2024b). The discussed uncertainties are summarized in Table 14.

Table 14. Summary of uncertainties, and notes of possible impact on the benefit of sea ice information.

Uncertainty factor	Notes of possible implication
Non-linearity of CO ₂ emissions	After a certain threshold, every additional unit of CO ₂ might cause rapidly growing damage and increase social avoided costs
CO ₂ price	SCC is higher than current EU ETS prices which indicates that the calculated avoided costs present a lower bound of avoided CO ₂ costs
Fuel price	Using specifically Arctic fuel prices might increase avoided fuel costs
Sea ice information accuracy	Higher accuracy indicates higher avoided costs
Share of service adoption	The number of users that really benefit of the service largely determine the magnitude of benefits that can be generated
Impact of the presence of predetermined routes and ice breaker assistance	If sea ice information has no impact on route optimizing, there might be no benefits generated through avoided fuel and CO ₂ costs. Ice breakers might generate avoided costs too, but also increase total fuel consumption and emissions
Lack of ice in the southern part of the study area	Some southern parts lack ice during the study periods of this analysis which causes biases that might overestimate the total avoided costs
Magnitude of fuel consumption and CO ₂ emissions that can be avoided	Higher level of avoided fuel consumption (effectiveness of information) increases the benefits

Uncertainty factor	Notes of possible implication
Omitted ice-class vessels	Including ice-class vessels could increase benefits. However, they are not assumed to benefit as much because of their better ability to navigate in icy waters

7.3 Policy implications

Aspects regarding shipping regulations and Arctic governance play a crucial role in Arctic GHG emission control and fuel usage as well on defining the shipping activity in the Arctic. These aspects are crucial in shaping the magnitude of economic benefits created through sea ice information. The International Maritime Organization (IMO) is a UN agency operating with issues related to the global maritime industry and is responsible of the governance of international shipping (AMSA Report, 2009; Huntington, 2023). In 2017, IMO's International Code for Ships Operating in Polar Waters (Polar Code) was entered into force. The Polar Code includes matters such as safety, environmental protection and equipment related topics that are relevant to shipping close to the two poles (IMO, 2024). The IMO GHG Strategy represents the international body that addresses GHG emissions from international shipping. The strategy supports and follows the guidelines including UN Conventions such as the Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS, 1982) and the Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC, 1994) as well as the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (IMO, 2023). The United Nations article 234 UNCLOS, provides a fundamental framework for the governance of Arctic marine navigation. The international Convention for the Prevention of Marine Pollution from Ships (MARPOL 1973/1978) seeks to prevent and minimize pollution from ships, both from operational and accidental causes, and to ensure the protection of the marine environment.

Since January 2023, all ships have been required to calculate their Energy Efficiency Existing Ship Index (EEXI) to measure how energy-efficient they are. Ships must also collect data to report their annual Carbon Intensity Indicator (CII) and CII rating. The CII measures a ship's energy efficiency based in grams of CO₂ emitted per cargo-carrying capacity and nautical mile. (IMO, 2024b)

Starting in 2024 IMO set a ban on certain uses of heavy fuel oil in the Arctic (Huntington et al., 2023). In addition, since January 2024, carbon dioxide emissions from vessels with gross tonnage (GT) of 5 000 and above have been incorporated into

the European Emissions Trading System (EU ETS). For voyages starting or ending outside the EU, 50% of the emissions are considered and for vessels operating inside the EU, 100% of the emissions are considered (European Commission, 2024a). This thesis does not distinguish which vessels sail under the impact of EU ETS and which not. However, under the current regulatory framework, some of the calculated external costs caused by CO₂ emissions within the EU borders are, in fact, private costs.

The FuelEU Maritime Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2023/1805), introduced under the European Commission's Fit for 55 legislative package, aims to advance the adoption of renewable, low-carbon fuels and clean energy technologies in the maritime sector. This regulation was fully enforced in January 2025 and obligates vessels above 5 000 GT calling at European ports to reduce GHG intensity of the energy used on board gradually over time starting with a 2% decrease by 2025 and reaching up to an 80% reduction by 2050. (European Commission, 2024b)

Eight countries including Canada, Finland, Iceland, Norway, Russia, Sweden, the United States and Denmark via Greenland have territory above the Arctic circle. However, Lavengood (2021) highlights that the most influence on the Arctic region have United States, Russia and China. A key challenge in Arctic shipping governance is making sure that also the concerns of small Arctic communities considering shipping impacts are heard in the national and international forums where rules are made (Shadian, 2014). Some progress has been made at the international level, such as the Inuit Circumpolar Council (ICC) becoming the first Indigenous organization to gain provisional status at the IMO (Huntington, 2023). Also, during 2021, the eight Arctic States (mentioned above) and the six Indigenous Permanent Participants celebrated a 25-year collaboration that remains unique in the world (Dalaklis et al., 2023).

Future Arctic shipping is dependent on the geopolitics of the area since issues regarding economic access and environmental stewardship remain unresolved. The geopolitics of the region has taken shape this far with multilateralism and diplomacy which is largely thanks to the Arctic Council (Lavengood, 2021). The Arctic Council is an intergovernmental forum consisting of the eight above mentioned countries that have territory within the Arctic (Arctic Council, 2024b). Protection of the Arctic Marine Environment (PAME) is one of six Arctic Council working groups. PAME focuses on activities related to protection and sustainable use of the Arctic marine environment (PAME, 2024). The Arctic Council has historically maintained peaceful relations even

in times of tensions rising far from the Arctic circle. The work of the Council covers issues tied to environmental protection and sustainable development. With the Russian invasion of Ukraine in February 2022 and the following pause in Arctic Council activities has questioned the future of Arctic Council and Arctic governance in general. This comes at a critical time when increasing environmental and geopolitical pressures demand heightened cooperation rather than division (Dyck, 2024). Besides the Arctic Council, the Arctic Coast Guard Forum, which includes all eight Arctic countries, plays a crucial role in Arctic cooperation and shipping governance by promoting safe, secure, and environmentally responsible maritime activities in the region (Huntington, 2023).

7.4 Avoided costs in the future

It is uncertain how the benefits of sea ice information are going to develop in the future. In the scenario analysis three different cases were studied. As shown in Table 13 in Chapter 6.5, all considered scenarios demonstrated higher benefits than costs with a 10% adoption rate, when the discount rate ranged from 1% to 7%. However, several other factors that were not considered in the scenario analysis and some of which may interact simultaneously, are likely to influence the future avoided costs and should be considered in future research.

In general, the number of conventional ice-class vessels is expected to increase in the future, reflecting growing interest in Arctic shipping. Increasing shipping activity is likely to exacerbate sea ice melt as black carbon emissions rise in relation to the rise of shipping traffic (Jiang et al., 2020). The number of winter sailings has increased in last years (Müller et al., 2023) and in this sense the benefits of sea ice information could be expected to increase if more ships are exposed to challenging ice conditions. However, the ice levels in the summer have declined by over 40% between 1979 and 2021 and a complete loss of summer sea ice is projected by 2030 (Wang and Overland, 2012) which could decrease demand for ice information and along that also the benefits of it.

Also, issues regarding economic access, environmental stewardship and tightened world political situation remain unsolved and could seed varying degrees of conflict in the future (Jiang et al., 2020). Economic factors, such as commodity prices, shipping schedules, port infrastructure, and insurance premiums will impact the future magnitude of Arctic shipping as well as regulatory challenges, including icebreaker

fees, ice-class vessel requirements, and national and international governance regimes (Stephenson & Smith, 2015).

Russia is developing and commissioning nuclear icebreakers designed to operate in the heavily ice-covered eastern region of the Northern Sea Route (NSR). These advancements are expected to enable regular year-round shipping along the entire NSR within the next 8 to 10 years (in 2021). The reduction of ice coverage and ice thickness as well as the improvements in icebreaking technology could shorten this timeframe further (Gunnarsson, 2021). These advancements assumably increase shipping traffic along the NSR in the future. The decision shipping operators make regarding the purchase of ice-class versus conventional vessels is critical, as ice-class ships are more likely to navigate without requiring icebreaker support. This is also crucial from the viewpoint of avoided costs generated through sea ice information since it is indicated by Arctic PASSION (2024b) that information about the riskiness of ice conditions is more valuable for ships with lower ice class and no ice class.

For shipping between the northern and southern part of the globe the Arctic routes may serve shorter transit times, lower fuel and overall costs, improve network connectivity and lower carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gas emissions (Theocharis et al., 2018). The decision between Arctic routes and southern alternatives influences the Arctic shipping activity and further the economic benefits generated through sea ice information. Multiple studies (for example Wang et al., 2021) suggest that using Arctic routes are, in fact, not as economically profitable as thought. In addition, some major corporations have decided not to ship via the Arctic at all because of environmental concern (Ocean Conservancy, 2024) potentially decreasing the interest on Arctic shipping further (Akbayirli & Tuna, 2022). The results in the literature indicate that, although Arctic routes can be more cost-effective and energy efficient when comparing to traditional routes, especially in the long term, they can mainly be used as seasonal alternatives for bulk and specialized shipping in the short term (Theocharis et al., 2018).

8 Conclusions

The aim of this thesis has been to answer the key research question: How much can be saved in private costs through fuel savings and in social costs through CO₂ reductions by using sea ice information in the Arctic? The results show the potential economic savings achievable through shorter shipping distances or reduced power usage. Every additional 1% avoided in total fuel consumption saves annually €2.8 million in fuel costs and €940 000 in CO₂ cost in the Arctic. Over the 6-month period (November to April), each additional 1% reduction in total fuel consumption results savings of €1.2 million in fuel costs and €390 000 in CO₂ costs per winter. The EEZ-level analysis shows that the greatest benefits, in terms of avoided costs, occur in the Alaskan EEZ, while the ship type-level analysis indicates that bulk carriers generate highest avoided costs. The scenario analysis conducted for the period from 2024 to 2100 shows that the present value of the benefits of sea ice information significantly outweighs the present value of costs of a representative sea ice service across the considered scenarios. Overall, the results indicate that producing sea ice information is feasible. However, the results include uncertainties and are based on multiple assumptions that provide many opportunities to expand this research.

Although CO₂ prices were included into the Monte Carlo Simulations, future research could use higher prices for CO₂ to better present the price of the social cost of carbon. Also, given that the CO₂ emissions of shipping are partly incorporated into EU ETS, a portion of CO₂ could be treated as private costs, rather than external costs, to better reflect the private costs. Another aspect for future research could be to consider that some Arctic areas have limited potential for route optimization due to different practices in icebreaker assistance and predetermined routes. Moreover, this thesis assessed the benefit of one additional percentage point reduction in total fuel consumption. However, the actual magnitude of the benefits depends on factors such as ice conditions and ship type. Understanding how the benefit generated through sea ice information varies among different vessels and areas would enable a comparison of the benefits of sea ice information across different times of the year, in regions with varying ice conditions and icebreaker assistance practices, and by each ship type and ice class. Also, the present value calculations could be expanded by considering additional factors that influence the benefits, as well as their combined impact. These

calculations could include assessing the impacts of different regulatory frameworks and climate change scenarios.

Further possibility to increase the scope of this analysis would be to add other benefits categories to better assess the total economic value of sea ice information, as this analysis only included benefits generated through avoided fuel and CO₂ costs. Future benefit assessments of sea ice information could include, for instance, avoided accident costs and the avoided environmental damage caused by externalities other than CO₂ emissions. One possibility would be to assess the benefits of improved ship navigation on local people and their livelihoods. A further aspect would be to assess the benefits of sea ice information for fishing vessels and ice-class vessels since they were excluded from this analysis. This could be done, for example, by assuming different benefit-levels for different ship types and ice classes. Additionally, a better understanding of the cost-efficiency of sea ice information as a CO₂ abatement option would enable comparisons with other abatement measures related to shipping emissions, providing decision-makers with valuable insights into effective ways to reduce marine emissions.

Given the narrow existing research on the economic benefits of sea ice information, this study provides initial insights about the benefits of sea ice information across the entire Arctic region and directions for further studies. Additionally, the results can aid ship operators recognize the critical role of sea ice information in managing cost flows, while also enabling regulators to understand better the economic importance of sea ice information services in climate change mitigation and adaptation efforts. Furthermore, the results give sea ice service providers insight into the benefits of their products in relation to production costs.

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